
Learning the galaxy-environment connection with graph neural networks

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Abstract

Galaxies co-evolve with their host dark matter halos. Models of the galaxy-halo connection, calibrated using cosmological hydrodynamic simulations, can be used to populate dark matter halo catalogs with galaxies. We present a new method for inferring baryonic properties from dark matter subhalo properties using message-passing graph neural networks (GNNs). After training on subhalo catalog data from the Illustris TNG300-1 hydrodynamic simulation, our GNN can infer stellar mass from the host and neighboring subhalo positions, kinematics, masses, and maximum circular velocities. We find that GNNs can also robustly estimate stellar mass from subhalo properties in $2d$ projection. While other methods typically model the galaxy-halo connection in isolation, our GNN incorporates information from galaxy environments, leading to more accurate stellar mass inference.

1. Introduction

In the current Λ CDM paradigm of hierarchical galaxy formation, the galaxy-halo connection is crucial for understanding how galaxies form and evolve, and for constraining the small-scale clustering of matter (Somerville & Davé, 2015; Wechsler & Tinker, 2018; Vogelsberger et al., 2020). Techniques for modeling the co-evolution of galaxies and dark matter range from simple, non-parametric approaches to full-physics magnetohydrodynamic simulations which require $> 10^8$ CPU hours of computation (Vale & Ostriker, 2004; Pillepich et al., 2018). Detailed simulations contribute important insights into galaxy formation, but due to their complexity and heavy computational costs, they are hard to analyze and cannot be performed for cosmologically signifi-

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cant volumes. Machine Learning (ML) is a natural option for making progress on both of these problems.

We present an equivariant Graph Neural Network (GNN), which takes as its input a graph composed of halos linked on a linking scale of 5 Mpc, and predicts baryonic properties. The GNN incorporates the effects of a galaxy’s environment, thereby improving the prediction of its baryonic properties compared to traditional methods. We are also able to train a network on the Illustris TNG300-1 box in 10 minutes on a single NVIDIA A10G GPU; inference takes one second. In this work, we focus on estimating stellar mass from a catalog of subhalo positions, velocities, M_{halo} , and V_{max} .

2. Related work

The connection between galaxies and their dark matter halos has been characterized via abundance matching or halo occupation distribution (HOD) models of central halos (Berlind & Weinberg, 2002; Wechsler et al., 2002), conditional luminosity or mass functions (Yang et al., 2003; Moster et al., 2010), subhalo abundance matching (Kravtsov et al., 2004; Vale & Ostriker, 2004; Conroy et al., 2006), and empirical models of the galaxy-halo connection (e.g., Reddick et al., 2013; Behroozi et al., 2019). Several works have also attempted to perform abundance matching or paint baryons (i.e., stars) onto dark matter maps by using classical machine learning algorithms (e.g., Kamdar et al., 2016; Agarwal et al., 2018; Calderon & Berlind, 2019) and/or neural networks (e.g., Zhang et al., 2019; Moster et al., 2021; Mohammad et al., 2022).

In general, these previous methods treat halo/galaxy systems as unrelated entities with no formation history. To rectify this, Villanueva-Domingo et al. (2022) construct mathematical graphs to represent group halos, and train a GNN to learn the central halo mass, which was later applied to estimate the halo masses of local Group galaxies (Villanueva-Domingo et al., 2021). GNNs have also been successfully used to model the dependence of galaxy properties on merger history (e.g., Jespersen et al., 2022; Tang & Ting, 2022), and generate synthetic galaxy catalogs (Jagvaral et al., 2022).

In cosmology, several works have already demonstrated the representational power of GNNs, and have used it for simulation-based inference (likelihood-free inference).

Figure 1. Cosmic graph of a TNG300 subvolume spanning approximately 45 Mpc. Subhalos live on nodes and are colored by their logarithmic subhalo mass. Edges are formed between pairs of subhalos separated by less than the linking length of 5 Mpc.

Villanueva-Domingo & Villaescusa-Navarro (2022) employ GNNs to infer the cosmological parameters Ω_m and σ_8 , using $3d$ galaxy positions and stellar properties from the CAMELS simulation suite (Villaescusa-Navarro et al., 2021). Makinen et al. (2022) show that GNNs can optimally extract and compress catalog data for cosmological parameter inference. Shao et al. (2023) and de Santi et al. (2023) train GNNs to infer cosmological parameters from dark matter-only simulations, and then validate their robustness on other N -body and hydrodynamic simulations.

3. Cosmic graphs

3.1. Simulation data

We use SUBFIND $z = 0$ subhalo catalogs (Springel et al., 2001) derived from the Illustris TNG300-1 hydrodynamic simulation (Nelson et al., 2019b; Pillepich et al., 2019). We split the full cosmological box into $6^3 = 216$ subvolumes in order to fit into 16 GB of memory, such that each subvolume is about $(50 \text{ Mpc})^3$. For consistency with the TNG simulations, we adopt the Planck Collaboration et al. (2016) cosmology and set $H_0 = 67.74 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

We select unflagged subhalos that have more than 50 star particles, $\log(M_*/M_\odot) > 9$, and $\log(M_{\text{halo}}/M_\odot) > 10$. Due to cosmic variance, some subvolumes only have a few hundred subhalos, while others have thousands. In Figure 1, we show an example of a typical subvolume.

3.2. Equivariant graph neural networks

We construct a mathematical graph for each TNG300 subvolume, such as the one depicted in Figure 1. We designate $\mathcal{V}_i = (\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{v}_i, M_{\text{halo},i}, V_{\text{max},i})$ as the eight node features. Subhalos within a linking length of $L = 5 \text{ Mpc}$ are connected with edges. Subvolumes are padded by 2.5 Mpc on each side, such that subvolumes do not share connections that would be relevant for the linking length. We allow nodes to be connected to themselves (i.e., self-loops). On each edge \mathcal{E}_{ij} , we compute three features: the squared Euclidean distance $d_{ij} \equiv \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^2$, the inner product between unit vectors $\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_j$, and the inner product between unit vectors $\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_{i-j}$, where unit vectors $\mathbf{e}_i \equiv (\mathbf{x}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}})/\|\mathbf{x}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}}\|$ are defined using positions \mathbf{x}_i relative to the centroid of the point cloud distribution $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, and \mathbf{e}_{i-j} is the unit vector in the direction of $\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j$.

We use a message-passing GNN based on the model described in Villanueva-Domingo et al. (2022). By design, the GNN is equivariant to permutations and invariant under the $E(3)$ group action, i.e., invariant to rotations, reflections, and translations. For more details about equivariant GNNs, see the appendices of Garcia Satorras et al. (2021) and Sections 3.1 and 3.2 of Villanueva-Domingo & Villaescusa-Navarro (2022). We aggregate layer inputs at each node by max pooling over information from neighboring nodes.¹ Our GNN has one set of fully connected layers with 256 latent channels and 128 hidden channels. We predict two quantities for each node, which correspond to the logarithmic stellar mass $y_i \equiv \log(M_{*,i}/M_\odot)$ and the logarithm of its variance Σ_i .

3.3. Optimization

Our loss function is composed of two terms: the mean squared error on the logarithmic stellar mass $\|\hat{\mathbf{y}} - \mathbf{y}\|^2$, and the squared difference between the measured and predicted logarithmic variance $\|(\hat{\mathbf{y}} - \mathbf{y})^2 - \hat{\Sigma}\|^2$. The second term ensures that uncertainties are appropriately estimated, which prevents mode collapse and enables robust likelihood estimation (e.g., useful for simulation-based inference, Jeffrey & Wandelt, 2020). We stabilize training by taking the logarithm of each loss term before summing them. We monitor the loss as well as the root mean squared error (RMSE) on $\log(M_*/M_\odot)$.

We perform $k = 6$ -fold cross-validation. For each fold, we train on 180 subvolumes and validate on 36 subvolumes, such that the validation set forms a $\sim 50 \times 300 \times 300 \text{ Mpc}^3$ subbox. We augment the training data set by randomly rotating positions and velocities while training the neural net-

¹We do not find significant improvements by using a concatenation of sum, max, mean, and variance aggregations, or by using learnable aggregation functions.

Figure 2. Predicted stellar mass versus true stellar mass for the TNG300 validation data. From left to right, we show results for a random forest (RF) trained only using M_{halo} , a RF trained only using V_{max} , a RF trained using both M_{halo} and V_{max} , and our GNN trained using \mathbf{p} , \mathbf{v} , M_{halo} , and V_{max} . We also report the scatter in the reconstructed $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot})$.

work (although these symmetries are inherent to the model). Based on a preliminary hyperparameters search, we implement a simple optimization schedule over a total of 1000 epochs using the AdamW optimizer (Kingma & Ba, 2014; Loshchilov & Hutter, 2017) and a batch size of 36. We begin with a learning rate of 10^{-2} and weight decay of 10^{-4} , and then decrease both by a factor of 5 at 500 epochs, and again decrease both by a factor of 5 at 750 epochs. We inspect the training and validation losses to ensure that the optimization is converged and does not overfit the training data.

4. Results

Overall, we find that the GNN can infer the stellar mass from subhalo properties with remarkable accuracy. We recover the galaxy stellar mass to within $\text{RMSE} = 0.129$ dex of its simulated value by using a GNN. The predictions are largely unbiased as a function of mass. We find that the scatter slightly increases for lower-mass subhalos, which we discuss further in §4.2.

4.1. Comparisons against baseline models

In Figure 2, we compare the performance of different ML models trained and cross-validated on the same TNG300 data set. The panels show, from left to right: a random forest (RF) trained using M_{halo} as input, a RF trained using V_{max} , a RF trained using both M_{halo} and V_{max} , and a GNN trained using $3d$ positions, $3d$ velocities, M_{halo} , and V_{max} .

Our baseline model for comparison uses a RF, which serves as a reasonable proxy for abundance matching or a conditional luminosity function (Calderon & Berlind, 2019). By comparing the left-most and left-center panels, we observe that V_{max} is more physically connected to M_{\star} than M_{halo} , in agreement with previous findings (e.g., Conroy et al., 2006; Reddick et al., 2013). A RF trained on both M_{halo} and V_{max} provides an even better reconstruction ($\text{RMSE} = 0.148$ dex). However, the neighboring subhalo

properties contribute additional information, as the GNN strongly outperforms the baseline models.

In Table 1, we list performance metrics for various RF and GNN models, including the RMSE, mean average error (MAE), normalized median absolute deviation (NMAD),² Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ), correlation of determination (R^2), bias, and outlier fraction ($> 3 \times \text{NMAD}$).

4.2. Centrals versus satellites

Satellite dark matter halos are preferentially stripped relative to stars in a host halo’s tidal field (Smith et al., 2016). In Appendix A we show the stellar mass-halo mass relation for satellite and central galaxies in TNG300 (Figure 3). Indeed, we observe that satellite galaxies exhibit significantly more dispersion than centrals $M_{\star}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation. Our $3d$ GNN is also worse at predicting $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot})$ for satellites than for centrals (see bottom two rows of Table 1), but this is due to the inherently larger scatter in the satellite-halo relation. We find that there is an overall negative bias for satellites and a positive bias for centrals, because the GNN must learn separate offset relations for both centrals and satellites.

4.3. Cosmic substructure in projection

We also construct cosmic graphs in projection, i.e. projected coordinates x_1 and x_2 , and radial velocity v_3 , instead of the full phase space information (see Appendix B). This $2d$ GNN model achieves $\text{RMSE} = 0.135$ dex scatter, which still exceeds the performance of the best RF estimator (see Table 1). Because the $2d$ GNN encode projected large scale structure information, it outperforms the RF models that can only learn isolated subhalo information.

²We define $\text{NMAD}(\mathbf{x}) \equiv k \cdot \text{median}(|x - \text{median}(\mathbf{x})|)$, where $k \approx 1.4826$ ensures that the NMAD and standard deviation are equal for a normally distributed \mathbf{x} .

Table 1. Cross-validation metrics for a variety of models discussed in the text. The GNN trained using positions, velocities, M_{halo} , and V_{max} achieves the best metrics (shown in bold) in nearly every category. The last two rows report metrics for the 3d GNN model, except that only central and satellite subhalos are selected, respectively. We repeat the entire training and cross-validation experiment three times; the scatter is too small to be shown in the displayed significant figures for all columns except the bias and outlier fraction.

Model	dim	RMSE (dex)	MAE (dex)	NMAD (dex)	Pearson ρ	R^2	Bias (10^{-3} dex)	Outlier fraction (%)
RF - M_{halo}	1	0.366	0.308	0.277	0.780	0.606	-0.0 ± 0.1	2.53 ± 0.01
RF - V_{max}	1	0.197	0.177	0.152	0.942	0.886	-0.3 ± 0.0	1.44 ± 0.01
RF - $M_{\text{halo}} + V_{\text{max}}$	2	0.148	0.135	0.114	0.967	0.936	0.3 ± 0.0	1.31 ± 0.00
GNN (2d projection)	5	0.135	0.131	0.106	0.973	0.946	-3.9 ± 2.2	0.68 ± 0.01
GNN (3d)	8	0.129	0.125	0.102	0.975	0.951	0.8 ± 0.6	0.68 \pm 0.00
GNN (3d) - centrals	8	0.123	0.119	0.097	0.979	0.959	4.6 ± 0.7	0.67 ± 0.01
GNN (3d) - satellites	8	0.138	0.136	0.109	0.968	0.936	-5.0 ± 0.6	0.58 ± 0.01

5. Discussion

We have presented a novel method for populating dark matter subhalos with galaxy stellar masses. Mathematical graphs combine individual halo properties and environmental parameters in an equivariant representation, resulting in robust predictions for both central and satellite galaxies. As shown in Table 1 and Figure 2, the cosmic graphs outperform random forests trained on V_{max} and M_{halo} . For galaxies with $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot}) \geq 9$ and $\log(M_{\text{halo}}/M_{\odot}) \geq 10$, we recover the logarithmic stellar mass to within a root mean squared error (RMSE) of 0.129 dex.

5.1. Inductive biases of GNNs

We note that previous works have employed convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for painting stars onto dark matter maps (Zhang et al., 2019; Mohammad et al., 2022). Unlike abundance matching models and RFs, CNNs are able to represent local spatial information. However, CNNs and GNNs have different inductive biases: CNNs are well-suited for representing fields discretized onto a Cartesian grid, while GNNs are well-suited for representing objects and relationships between them. Galaxies have small sizes (\sim kpc) relative to their typical separations (\sim Mpc), and they interact with each other (and their surrounding media) through multiple physical mechanisms (e.g., gravitational attraction, tides, ram pressure, etc). Therefore, cosmic structures naturally conform to a graphical representation, motivating our use of GNNs in this work.

5.2. Galaxy environments

We note that a GNN with no edges except self-loops would essentially model the galaxy-halo connection in isolation; all environmental information is contained and passed along the edges. However, if we remove self-loops from the GNN, then the GNN is still able to infer $\log(M_{\star}/M_{\odot})$ to within RMSE \sim 0.145 dex. A GNN without self-loops must es-

timate galaxy stellar mass *solely* from neighboring halo information, which demonstrates that galaxy environments are informative for modeling the galaxy-halo connection.

We find that the GNN with max-pooling aggregation function achieves 0.001 dex lower RMSE than a GNN with sum-pooling. This result suggests that the GNN selects the largest value for some combination of M_{halo} , V_{max} , and distance to neighboring subhalos in order to best make predictions. We can tentatively interpret this as evidence that the largest and most nearby subhalo is most informative to a GNN. The largest subhalo might dominate environmental effects (e.g. tides and ram pressure) and control a given subhalo’s stellar mass. Meanwhile, the summed information should capture *all* of the forces, and we expect it to be more robust or transferable across domains. We plan to do an exhaustive hyperparameter search over GNN architecture and optimization procedures in a follow-up work.

5.3. Applications to observations and domain shift

The strong performance of 2d GNNs (§4.3) is promising for facilitating comparisons to observations beyond the Local Group, where we can only reliably measure projected positions and line-of-sight velocities rather than full phase space information. Our method can be used to quickly estimate galaxy properties of constrained N -body (McAlpine et al., 2022) and Gpc-scale N -body simulated volumes (Garrison et al., 2018; Maksimova et al., 2021) for comparison with wide-area galaxy surveys in the low-redshift Universe (Ruiz-Macias et al., 2021; Carlsten et al., 2022; Darragh-Ford et al., 2022; Driver et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022).

Domain adaptation will likely be needed to ensure simulated results can transfer to observations (e.g. Ciprijanovic et al., 2023). As a preliminary test, we repeat our experiment by training on TNG300 and validating on TNG50 data, and vice versa; in both cases the results are poor ($>$ 0.2 dex). However, by training on a subset both simulations, we

can recover $\log(M_*/M_\odot)$ to ~ 0.13 dex for TNG300 and ~ 0.14 dex for TNG50 (Nelson et al., 2019a;b). This test suggests that cross-domain applications, such as transferring GNN results from simulations to observations, will necessitate some form of domain adaptation.

Software and Data

Our code is completely public on Github, and the URL will be provided here after anonymous review. We have used the following software and tools: `numpy` (Harris et al., 2020), `matplotlib` (Hunter, 2007), `pandas` (Wes McKinney, 2010), `pytorch` (Paszke et al., 2019), and `pytorch-geometric` (Fey & Lenssen, 2019).

We only use public simulation data from Illustris, which can be downloaded from <https://www.tng-project.org/data/>.

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A. The stellar mass-halo mass relation for satellites and centrals

In Figure 3, we show halo masses and stellar masses for central galaxies (red) and satellites (blue) from the TNG300 SUBFIND catalogs. Our GNN is able to learn the offset relationships for both central and satellite subhalos.

B. Cosmic graphs in projected coordinates

In §4.3, we trained a GNN to learn the galaxy-halo connection using projected positions and radial velocity, in addition to M_{halo} and V_{max} . In Figure 4, we show a projected version of the subvolume that appeared in Figure 1.

Figure 3. The stellar mass-halo mass relation in TNG300 for satellite and central galaxies.

Figure 4. A graph of galaxies in projection, analogous to Figure 1. Subhalos now connected with edges if their projected distances are less than 5 Mpc.